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CLINICAL EXAMPLES OF CARDIOMYOPATHY IN CHILDREN

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8318739>

ANNOTATION

Among cardiovascular diseases, cardiomyopathies are the most severe diseases in children, characterized by heart rhythm disturbances, thromboembolic complications and frequent fatal outcomes in the form of sudden cardiac death [9]. The study aimed to identify risk factors for cardiomyopathies (CMD) in children. Materials and methods of the study were 2 clinical examples who were hospitalized in the cardioreumatology department of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Pediatrics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: restrictive cardiomyopathy, children, cardiomyopathy, dilated cardiomyopathy.

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КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИМЕРЫ КАРДИОМИОПАТИЙ У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

На сегодняшний день среди заболеваний сердечно-сосудистой патологии кардиомиопатии являются наиболее тяжелыми заболеваниями у детей, для них характерны нарушения ритма сердца, тромбоэмболические осложнения и частый фатальный исход в виде внезапной сердечной смерти [9]. Целью исследования явилось выявление факторов риска развития кардиомиопатий (КМП) у детей. Материалы и методы исследования явились 2 клинических примеров, которые были госпитализированы в кардиоревматологическое отделение Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра педиатрии Министерства здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: рестриктивная кардиомиопатия, дети, кардиомиопатия, дилатационная кардиомиопатия.

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BOLALARDA KARDIOMIOPATIYA KLINIK NAMUNALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bugungi kunga kelib, yurak-qon tomir patologiyasi kasalliklari orasida kardiomyopatiya bolalardagi eng og'ir kasallik bo'lib, ular yurak aritmi, tromboembolik asoratlar va to'satdan yurak o'limi ko'rinishidagi tez-tez o'limga olib keladigan natijalar bilan tavsiflanadi [9]. Tadqiqotning maqsadi bolalarda kardiomyopatiya (KMP) rivojlanishi uchun xavf omillarini aniqlash edi. O'rganish materiallari va usullari O'zbekiston Respublikasi Sog'liqni saqlash vazirligi Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan pediatriya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazining kardio-revmatologiya bo'limiga yotqizilgan 2 ta klinik holat bo'ldi.

Kalit so'zlar: cheklovchi kardiomyopatiya, bolalar, kardiomyopatiya, dilate kardiomyopatiya.

Introduction. Non-coronary myocardial diseases (NCMD) remain one of the most challenging problems in pediatrics. Due to high-tech methods of diagnosis and treatment, the last century has seen a significant improvement in prognosis and increased life expectancy in patients with ischemic heart and brain disease. However, morbidity and mortality from cardiomyopathies and myocarditis remained at the same level [1, 2, 3]. Non-coronagenic changes in myocardium are determined in 20-40% of fatal outcomes in children who died from sudden death syndrome at the age from birth to 18 years [4, 6]. Cardiomyopathies and myocarditis occupy a special place among NCMD in children.

In the last 10 years, an increase in the incidence of CMP among adults and children has been noted; this is due to the improvement of diagnostics due to the introduction of highly informative instrumental methods of cardiac imaging, primarily echodopplercardiography, as well as to the streamlining of ideas about cardiomyopathy as a nosological unit [5, 7, 8].

CMPs are the most severe diseases in children, characterized by cardiac rhythm disturbances, thromboembolic complications and frequent fatal outcome in the form of sudden cardiac death [7].

Clinical classification is important to understand the problem and information about the nature of the disease, especially the disease group. This is important especially for myocardial diseases not associated with coronary artery disease (hence the most used group term - non-coronary myocardial diseases, NCMD), which with congenital and acquired heart defects are the most numerous, heterogeneous and insufficiently studied group of heart diseases [5].

The term "cardiomyopathies" was proposed by W. Brigden in 1957 to designate myocardial diseases of unknown nature (not associated with inflammation, CHD, hypertension, etc.) characterized by cardiomegaly, ECG changes, progressive course with the development of heart failure and unfavorable prognosis [3].

The introduction of this concept determined the formation of basic ideas about the three main mechanisms of primary myocardial damage - inflammation, dystrophy and genetic inferiority of structural proteins and other components of cardiomyocytes.

Clinical Cases:

1. Boy H.I., 2 years old, weight 8.5 kg, height 78 cm. According to the mother's words, the child is bothered by shortness of breath at rest and with minor physical activity, rapid fatigability, emotional lability, poor appetite, cyanosis of the nasolabial triangle, occasional cough, abdominal pain.

From the anamnesis: a child from the 4th pregnancy, the 3rd child. Pregnancy proceeded with toxicosis in the first trimester. The labor was rapid. The child was born with a weight of 3760.0 g, body length - 58 cm.

According to the mother, the child was admitted to the intensive care unit of the Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center at the place of residence with complaints of cough,

shortness of breath, rapid fatigue, decreased appetite, and increased body temperature up to 38°C at the age of 2.5 months. Before admission, a pediatrician examined the child and received DPT vaccine.

The child was examined, clinical and functional (electrocardiography (ECG)), instrumental (chest X-ray) and laboratory (general blood count, blood biochemistry, coagulogram) examinations were carried out, according to the results of which and clinical and anamnestic data the diagnosis "Out-of-hospital bronchopneumonia. Acute myocarditis".

Lymphocytosis was detected in the general blood test.

ECG showed signs of right ventricular hypertrophy, sinus tachycardia.

On chest X-ray cardiothoracic index (CTI) was 0.65. The heart was spherically dilated. The arcs are not clearly differentiated. Congestion in the lungs.

The child's condition worsened, the child was transferred 6 days later to the intensive care unit of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care.

Against the background of complex therapy with anti-inflammatory, antibacterial therapy positive dynamics was noted. The child was transferred to the somatic department, the child was treated in the hospital for 40 days.

In April 2018, in a serious condition with complaints of swelling of the extremities, cough, shortness of breath, decreased appetite, vomiting, the child was admitted to the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Pediatrics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the diagnosis of "Out-of-hospital bronchopneumonia. Acute myocarditis".

Clinical and functional (ECG, EchoCG, ECG Holter monitoring), laboratory (general hematologic analysis, biochemical blood analysis, as well as blood analysis for cardiac-specific markers - creatine phosphokinase, CPK-MB, lactate dehydrogenase, natriuretic peptide) and instrumental (chest X-ray) methods of examination were performed.

Objectively low body weight (weight 8.5 kg, height 78 cm), skin is clean, pale. Rales are heard in the lungs on both sides, respiratory rate - up to 44 per minute.

Apex thrust on the left side is distinct, heart boundaries are dilated on all sides, heart tones are deaf, rhythm is rhythmic, heart rate is increased - heart rate 125 per minute, liver enlargement up to +2.0 cm +2.5 cm +2.5 cm + 2.5 cm, pastosity of extremities.

During the examination in biochemical blood tests there was found an increase of natriuretic peptide up to 1200 pg/mL (norm 0-125 pg/mL), creatine phosphokinase up to 228 U/L (norm 24-190 U/L), CPK-MB - 35.5 ED/L (norm 1-24 U/L), lactate dehydrogenase - up to 1300 U/L (norm 225-450 U/L).

ECG showed sinus tachycardia (heart rate - 145 per minute), electrical axis shifted to the right, repolarization disorder, signs of right ventricular hypertrophy.

According to Holter monitoring data, there were average daytime (from 110 to 146 per minute) and nighttime (from 76 to 100 per minute) heart rate, as well as single polymorphic (up to 1500 per day) extrasystoles, tachycardia runs.

On EchoCG: left ventricular (LV) end-diastolic dimension - 30 mm, left ventricular (LV) end-systolic dimension - 15 mm, LV end-diastolic volume - 27 ml, ejection fraction - 65 % (according to I. Teicholz); hypertrabecularity of the right ventricle, double layer of myocardium was noted (Fig. 5.1).

Figure 5.1. Echocardiogram of b-y H., 2 years old with noncompact myocardium. Left heart dilatation with noncompaction of the myocardium in the four-chamber position.

Maximum myocardial thickening reached 1.05 cm with myocardial thickness in unchanged areas up to 0.4

cm (N/C ratio was 2.6). Intertrabecular gaps were more than 3. Moderate trabecularity of LV walls.

Considering the analysis of the conducted examinations, the child was diagnosed with a noncompaction form of cardiomyopathy. Complications: Heart failure stage II B. White-energy nutritional deficiency (-2 CO).

Against the background of complex therapy for correction of heart failure the condition remained relatively stable and severe.

2. Girl H.N., 15 years old, weight 50 kg, height 140 cm. In January 2019, the child was admitted to the RSNPMC of Pediatrics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a diagnosis of "Restrictive cardiomyopathy" in a serious condition with complaints from the mother about swelling of the extremities, cough, shortness of breath, decreased appetite.

From the anamnesis: according to the mother's words, the child is from the 2nd pregnancy. Pregnancy proceeded with toxicosis in the first trimester. The labor was rapid. The child was born with a weight of 3010.0 g and a body length of 50 cm. The child had an acute respiratory infection, hepatitis A.

According to the mother, the disease began in 2009 with shortness of breath, rapid fatigue. On admission, the child's condition was severe. Dyspnea, cyanosis of the nasolabial triangle, dry skin, decreased appetite were noted.

On auscultation of the lungs against the background of rigid breathing, wire rales were heard on both sides, heart tones were muffled, systolic murmur at the apex, accent of the second tone over the pulmonary artery. HR - 108 beats per min. BP - 90 over 60 mmHg. BP - 26 per min. The tongue is covered with white plaque.

On palpation the abdomen is soft, painless. The liver at palpation is compacted, protrudes from the subcostal area by +15 mm, +12 mm, +13 mm.

Clinical and functional (ECG, EchoCG, ECG Holter monitoring), laboratory (general hematologic analysis, biochemical blood analysis, as well as blood analysis for cardiac-specific markers - creatine phosphokinase, CPK-MB, lactate dehydrogenase, natriuretic peptide) and instrumental (chest X-ray, ultrasound examination of the liver, spleen, kidneys) examination methods were performed.

The general blood test revealed iron deficiency anemia, acceleration of COE.

In the course of examination in biochemical blood tests there was found an increase of natriuretic peptide up to 1200 pg/mL (norm 0-125 pg/mL), creatine phosphokinase up to 300 U/L (norm 24-190 U/L), CPK-MB - lactate dehydrogenase up to 570 U/L (norm up to 225-450 U/L), de Ritis index was increased up to 2.7 (ALT/AST in norm up to 1.5).

The ECG showed signs of sinus tachycardia. Incomplete blockade of the right bundle branch of Hiss, signs of ischemia of LV's anterior and lateral walls. According to Holter monitoring data, there were average daytime (from 86 to 130 per minute) and nighttime (from 90 to 110 per minute) heart rate, as well as single polymorphic (up to 100 per day) extrasystoles, tachycardia runs.

The cardiothoracic index (CTI) on chest radiography was 0.44, right-sided pleurisy.

On liver ultrasound, the picture of liver cirrhosis, portal hypertension, ascites.

EchoCG showed left ventricular end-diastolic dimension (LV) - 37 mm, left ventricular end-systolic dimension (LV) - 24 mm, LV end-diastolic volume - 61 ml, ejection fraction - 60% (according to Simpson), diastolic ventricular dysfunction, atrial dilatation - PP 51x40 mm, 50x40 mm, I-stage NIC (Fig. 5.2).

**Fig.5.2 Echocardiogram of b-y N., 15 years old.
Diagnosis: Restrictive cardiomyopathy**

Considering the results of the examination, clinical and anamnestic data, the child was diagnosed with restrictive cardiomyopathy, complications:

chronic heart failure II-B degree, in the stage of decompensation according to NYHA III class, liver cirrhosis, right-sided exudative pleurisy, ascites, anemia degree. The condition remained relatively stable and severe in the background of complex therapy for the correction of heart failure.

Thus, cardiomyopathies in children are severe and progressive diseases, which can be complicated by thromboembolic complications and heart rhythm disorders, leading to fatal outcomes.

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